

The Context of Shrikrishnakirtan in 'Bichitra' Patrika

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Summary:

The first and only evidence of ancient times is 'Charyapad'. Srikrishnakirtan is an important sign after 'Charyapade'. In 1316, Basantaranjan Raya Biddvallabha Mahashay found this manuscript along with many other manuscripts from the cowshed of Devendranath Mukhopadhyay of Kankilya village in Bankura at Bishnupur. Later in 1318, the manuscripts was collected and kept in the 'Bangiya Sahitya Parishada'. The second edition of the manuscripts was in 1319 by Basantaranjan Ray Published in 'Sahitya Parishad Patrika'. But 'Srikrishnakirtan' was published in 1323 i.e. five years later as a book. Ever since the publication of SriKrishnaKirtan, many controversies have arisen on its various issues, which continue even in the 21st century. Generally, there are many questions about 'Shrikrishnakirtan' such as when the poetry was written, what was the name and who was the poet etc. Even doubts have arisen whether the book is genuine or fake. Various essays are continuously published on 'Shrikrishnakirtan' in 'Bichitra' journal. While reading the essays are generally encounter some criticisms about the essays. Generally four essays were published in 'Bichitra' journal on 'Shrikrishnakirtan'. Namely –

1. "Srikrishnakirtan Chinnapatra"
2. "Chandidas and Rajakini of Srikrishnakirtan",
3. "Social Information in Srikrishnakirtan" and
4. "Shrikrishnakirtan manuscript's Scriptural".

Now as per the discussion of the essays we have to see that what controversy has arisen about 'Shrikrishnakirtan' and how far that controversy has been justified. In order to get a fuller account of 'Shrikrishnakirtan' the relevant parts of the history of Bengali literature, various Authors' books on 'Shrikrishnakirtan' must be a text. My present purpose is to introduce the debates.

Index Word: Srikrishnakirtan, Manuscripts, Chandidas, Bichitra Patrika, Name problem.

Main Essay:

The problem of Composition period of the Manuscript

It is very important for us to know the composition period of any manuscript. We can know the era of the manuscript only through the time of the script. A discussion of Nalininath Dasgupta's essay "Shrikrishnakirtan Manuscript's script" in 'Bichitra' helps us to understand the time period of the script. The author has tried to give a fixed period of 'Shrikrishnakirtan' through various arguments. It is better to say at the beginning, that he refuses Rakhaldas Bandyopadhyay's view and argues that Rakhaldas Bandyopadhyay's argument is not reasonable. A part from this, he expressed doubt in accepting the opinion of Basantaranjan Ray Biddyaballabha and Haraprasad Shastri. Rakhaldas Bandyopadhyay, after a long examination of the manuscript of Srikrishnakirtan, has come to the conclusion that the manuscript of Srikrishnakirtan is probably dated to the first half of the 14th century. Sunithikumar Chatterjee also supported this view¹. But the author Without accepting Rakhaldas Bandyopadhyay's opinion, he said –

Judging all aspects of this form, it can be roughly estimated that the manuscript of Krishna Kirtan, was written between the sixteenth century and early seventeenth century. It is possible that it is written at the end of the

16th century. If the manuscript belongs to this time, whether it affects the language of the book, it is not judged here, but in the language of 'আ-কার' (a-kar) and 'ঁ'(chandrabindu) it may not affect the language².

The author said in the above statement 'judging all such aspects' - now let's talk about the judgments he made –

Rakhaldas Bandyopadhyay has mentioned three texts over the period. Namely 'Sudrapaddhati', whose composition is dated from 1442 BC i.e. 1385/86, 'Byodhicharyabatar', whose composition dates from 1492 BC i.e. 1436/37 AD; 'Dharmaratna', which was written before 1417 century i.e. 1495 AD. So Rakhaldas Bandyopadhyay said during the writing period of these three books - the letters of 'Shrikrishna Kirtan' are older than the letters used in these three books written between 1385 AD and 1495 AD. But the author is of this opinion Arguing against this -

More than three-fourths of the ancient letters used in Krishnakirtan are not used in the above texts. Therefore, it is a definite conclusion that Mr. Basantaranjan Raya Viddvallabha Mahasaya "discovered the manuscript of Krishna-Kirtan, probably written before 1385 AD, probably in the first half of the fourteenth century AD."- But the 'Sudrapaddhati' book was not written in 1442 Bikramage, but in 1442 AD

or 1520 AD., and this is what Mahamahopadhyay Haraprasad Shastri Mahashay had also admitted (Sahitya Parisadh Patrika,1326, second issue)³.

Then it cannot be accepted that the book 'Dharmaratna' was also written in 1417 century. So Basantaranjan Roy Biddvallabh Mahashay's 'second speech' has a different tone. The letters used in Rakhaldas Bandyopadhyay's 'Shrikrishnakirtan' are in ancient form.

He thought that the letters 'ঊ(u), 'ঋ(ri), 'খ(kh), 'ঘ(gh), 'ঢ(dh), 'থ(th), 'ফ(f), 'ভ(v), 'ম(m), 'য(j) and 'ল(l) used in the Srikrishnakirtan were in ancient form. That is why these letters are used in the inscriptions like Laksman Sen, Tamra Shasana etc. But the author does not call the above letters ancient. But he has given sufficient reason behind it. Namely –

1. 'ঊ' - This was generally practiced till the end of the eighteenth century. An example of which can be found by looking for six manuscript written by different scribes of the eighteenth century.
2. 'ঋ' - According to the author, no instance of 'ঋ' of this shape has been discovered in any ancient Tamra Shasana manuscript or inscription manuscript.
3. 'ভ' - Rakhaldas Bandyopadhyay admits that 'ভ' in 'Shrikrishnakirtan' is the same as 'ভ' used in 'Sudrapaddhati', 'Byodhicharyavatar', 'Dharmaratna'. But the author did not accept this argument and said - 'ভ' is found in 'One manuscript of Angadaraibar's⁴ written in 1673 AD and 'ভ' like 'ভ' in 'Srikrishnakirtane' in 'One manuscript of Jaimini Bharate⁵ written in 1767 AD.
4. 'খ' - 'খ' of 'Angadaraibare' is more similar than 'খ' of Devpara.
5. 'ঘ' - 'ঘ' of 'Srikrishnakirtan' with the lower part of Bama Bagh and 'ঘ' of Senyuga.

Find the lesser the resemblance, but the greater resemblance we find eighteenth-century Jaimini in India. Apart from the above characters, many more characters are identified, which are also mentioned in the manuscript of the seventeenth-eighteenth century. So in support of the author's comments Sukumar Sen says –

In my opinion the writing of Sri Krishna Kirtan was not written then before the latter half of the eighteenth century perhaps belongs the nineteenth century. There is no obstacle in the terms of letters. Letters like the old verses of Srikrishnakirtan have been seen a lot in eighteenth century manuscript.⁶

Chandidas Problem (Poet Problem)

Pramatha Chowdhury's first essay in 'Bichitra' about 'Shrikrishnakirtan' is "Chinnapatra of Srikrishnakirtan". The essay highlighted on the Chandidas problem. It was the task of the author to determine whether the Chandidas of 'Sri Krishna Kirtan' and the Chandidas of Padavali are the same or different. Pramatha Chowdhury therefore said in the words of Sunitikumar Chattopadhyay –

The most complex problem related to Chandidas can be said in the history of Bengali Literature.⁷

Basantaranjan Ray Bidvallabh, however, Srikrishnakirtan's Chandidas and Padavali Chandidas are did not see Chandidas separately, that is, he saw him as one. Basantaranjan Roy's speech without support, the author says that

In our opinion Chandidas is the poet and the poet of Srikrishnakirtan is the poet. Of course, there are strong differences of opinion on this matter, and it is inevitable that there should be, because people have different tastes. And those who have tried to open our eyes of knowledge, also to exploit our taste could not So arguing about it is futile. The conversion of Pathak Pandit as a result of this meeting is the real problem about Chandidas.⁸

The author mentions two fragments discovered by Manindramohan Bose and suggests that they may solve the Chandidas problem. Manindramohan Bose's discovery of manuscript seems to help us on the subject of the antiquity of Chandidas -

On Saturday 8th Ashwin last, Mr. Manindramohan Bose was rummaging through a 'messy' cupboard of the University with 'Vanita' by Baru Chandidas.⁹

Linguist Mr. Sunithikumar Chatterpadhyay and Pedagogist Mr. Harekrishna Mukhopadhyay have said about this manuscript of Manindramohan Bose -**The main note worthy discovery about Chandidas, which complicates the Chandidas problem, It is done by Manindra Babu of this Shrikrishnakirtan. The invention of the modern feminine duality of the term.¹⁰**

Another controversy in the Chandidas problem is the date of composition of 'Srikrishnakirtana'. About this, Sunitibabu and Harekrishnababu said –

Shrikrishnakirtan is a work of the Chaitanya era; it is becoming clear to us.¹¹ That is, they said that 'Shrikrishnakirtan is very ancient. Mahaprabhu and Chandidas in the role of Basantaranjan Roy Biddvallabh in 'Srikrishnakirtan'. Even if the verse is composed, it cannot be said that Chandidas is not the Chandidas we know- Adi Chandidas. Narahari Das mentions Chandidas as the original poet. However All the verse(pad) used by Vaishnavdas, the compiler of 'Padakalpataru', are all It is said that Mahaprabhu Padavali used to listen to Chandidas' Padakirtana - Manindramohan Bose and Dr. Shrikumar Bandyopadhyay considers Chandidas, a

pre-Chaitanya poet, and Chandadas (Deen or Dwija), a post-Chaitanya poet.

And so finally I can say that there will be no end to the controversy over Chandidas. The problem that arose eight long decades ago remains a problem today.¹²

Name Problem

In the preface to 'Srikrishnakirtane', Ramendrasundar remarked that by adopting it various questions would be asked and the answer to each question would be debated among the scholars. That judgment continues even today, and one of the main issues is the naming of the book. The third essay in 'Bichitra' is Nalininath Dasgupta's "Shrikrishnakirtan, Social Information". Looking at the title of this essay, we may think that how the discussion of naming can come in the essay. But the author spends a few sentences on the naming of Shrikrishnakirtan. -

For a long time I had only heard about the existence of Krishna Kirtan composed by Chandidas. We believe that what is in question is 'Krishna Kirtan' and hence its similar name is suggested (Editorial statement, page no. 10).¹³

The author did not want to accept Basantaranjan Ray's 'Shrikrishnakirtan' as Srikrishnakirtan composed by Chandidas of Padavali. He thus says, The existence of Krishnakirtans which one hears about is not the work of any 'Chandidas' alone.¹⁴ He also wants to refer to Mr. Wilson's comment that Mr. Wilson did not say that Chandidasa of Padavali and Chandidasa of Srikrishnakirtan are one and the same. Wilson's book mentions 'Krishnakirtan by Vidyapati and Govindadas. In Wilson's words –

Other Sanskrit works are enumerated among the authorities of the seet [Vaisnab] as the Chaitanya Chandrodaya, a drama, Stava Mala, Stamrita Lahari by Visvananth Chakravarti, Bhajanamrita, Sri Smarana Darpana by Ramchandra Kaviraja, the Golpremanmrita, commentary on the Krishnakarnamerita by Krishna das. kaviraja, and the Krishna Kritana by Govinda das and Vidyapati.¹⁵

In 1282 Bengal, Jagabandhu Bhadra presented the subject of Krishnakirtan by citing Wilson and Wilson says Krishnakirtan was written by both Chandidasa and Govinda Dasa.

Author Vasantaranjan Ray's untitled manuscript denies the Srikrishnakirtana name said- **But the 'Krishna Kirtan' of Ananta Nama Baru Chandidas, the mind does not want to admit it, is an absolute proof. Who knows, maybe the real 'Krishna Kirtan' will come out one day, maybe it will be seen then. Mr. Wilson's statement is correct. If that day comes, it will be a shame as much as an outrage. Earlier, Baru Chandidas's poetry name was changed to 'Krishnamangale', there is no fear.**

But until the change is achieved, the name 'Krishna Kirtan' will remain.¹⁶

We don't know how to solve this naming problem. However, there is still a debate about this name problem in the scholarly circles. Nilratan Sen said so-

Chandidas is said to have composed Krishnakirtan poetry. Chandidas's Krishnalila was sung in one of the remaining festivals of Khetri, but in kirtana. The manuscript thesis that naming 'Shrikrishnakirtan' is not inappropriate.¹⁷

Muhammad Shahidullah,¹⁸ Bijanbehari Bhattacharya, Asitkumar Bandyopadhyay etc. have again assumed the title of the book to be "Shrikrishna Sandarbha". The assumption that the Srikrishnakirtan was titled "Srikrishnasandarbha" is based on the loose paper or receipt of Srikrishnakirtan which contains the name 'Srikrishnasandarbha'. From all these facts we can say that 'Shrikrishnakirtan' may be named 'Shrikrishna Sandarbha', but it is very difficult to prove it. So without going into that debate, I can say it will continue. As long as there is no change, the name Krishnakirtan.

Social context

Nalininath Dasgupta's 'Srikrishnakirtane Social Information' essay in 'Bichitra' journal has discussed the social picture of 'Srikrishnakirtane' in detail. All the social issues of that time are mentioned in Srikrishnakirtan. They are

1. Social reform trends at that time,
2. Obey social restrictions,
3. Use of men's and women's clothing,
4. Paying taxes,
5. Use of weapons,,
6. Provide entertainment system,
7. Caste judgment etc.

A part from this, the deplorable acts of keeping women in one room, killing women etc. were prevalent in the society as that time. The custom of paying tax on place-time-pot was also common. of various weapons A part from the usage, there was a kind of men's sport which was prevalent in the society of that time

Entertainer of entertainment. A discussion of the above essay published in 'Bichitra' helps us to give an idea of the scriptural, poet and name problems, and society of manuscript of Srikrishnakirtana. Through the various arguments of different authors, 'Shrikrishnakirtan' has encouraged us on various aspects of poetry, as well as left us with doubts about various issues. "There is no doubt that Baru Chandidas is the poet of Srikrishnakirtana, because Baru Chandidas's poetry appears in almost eighty percent of the verses in 'Srikrishnakirtan'. However, it should be noted at the end that this poem about Radha-Krishna conveys to us a sweet beauty.

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